

Diffrent functional equations of Riemann zeta function and its derivatives.

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I repeated the calculations for functional equation Riemann zeta function for diffrent integral which I found in Gradshtein I.S., Ryzhik I.M. Tables of integrals, series and products (7 ed., AP, 2007).Chapter 4.35 – 4.36 :

$$\int_0^{\infty} x^{z-1} e^{-nx} \ln(x) dx = \frac{\Gamma(z)}{n^z} [\psi(z) - \ln(n)],$$

$$\psi(z) = \frac{\Gamma'(z)}{\Gamma(z)}, \text{ Re}(z) > 0, \text{ Re}(n) > 0, z \in \mathbb{C}, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Hence

$$\int_0^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} \ln(x) dx = \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)}{(n^2 \pi)^{\frac{z}{2}}} \left[\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(n^2 \pi) \right] =$$

$$\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)}{(n^2)^{\frac{z}{2}}} \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(n^2 \pi) \right] =$$

$$\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)}{n^z} \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - 2 \ln(n) - \ln(\pi) \right] =$$

$$\frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - 2 \ln(n) - \ln(\pi) \right] =$$

$$\frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) - \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} 2 \frac{\ln(n)}{n^z} =$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\frac{1}{n^z} \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) - 2 \frac{\ln(n)}{n^z} \right]$$

writing $\theta(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-n^2 \pi x}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{hence } \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} \ln(x) dx &= \int_0^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\frac{1}{n^z} \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) - 2 \frac{\ln(n)}{n^z} \right] = \\
&= \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 2 \left(- \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln(n)}{n^z} \right) \right] = \\
&= \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 2 \zeta'(z) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{because } \theta(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{hence } \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 2 \zeta'(z) \right] &= \int_0^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \ln(x) dx + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= -\frac{2}{(z-1)^2} + \frac{2}{z^2} + \int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-\frac{3}{2}} \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \ln(x) dx + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \frac{2}{z^2} - \frac{2}{(1-z)^2} + \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \left(-\ln\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)\right) dx + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \frac{2}{z^2} - \frac{2}{(1-z)^2} + \int_{\infty}^1 (t)^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}} (t) \theta(t) \left(-\ln(t)\right) \left(\frac{-1}{t^2}\right) dt + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \frac{2}{z^2} - \frac{2}{(1-z)^2} + \int_{\infty}^1 x^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}} \theta(x) \ln(x) \left(\frac{1}{x}\right) dx + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \frac{2}{z^2} - \frac{2}{(1-z)^2} - \int_1^{\infty} x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \frac{2}{z^2} - \frac{2}{(1-z)^2} - \int_1^{\infty} x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx + \int_1^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
&= \frac{2}{z^2} - \frac{2}{(1-z)^2} + \int_1^{\infty} \left(x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} - x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \theta(x) \ln(x) dx
\end{aligned}$$

The right – hand side is changed only by minus if z is replaced by $1 - z$.

Hence

$$\begin{aligned}
\Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}} \left[\zeta(1-z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 2 \zeta'(1-z) \right] &= \\
\int_0^{\infty} x^{\frac{1-z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx &= \int_0^{\infty} x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = \\
\frac{2}{(z-1)^2} - \frac{2}{z^2} + \int_1^{\infty} \left(x^{\frac{1-z}{2}-1} - x^{-\frac{(1-z)}{2}-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \theta(x) \ln(x) dx &=
\end{aligned}$$

$$-\left[\frac{2}{z^2} - \frac{2}{(z-1)^2} + \int_1^{\infty} \left(x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} - x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\right) \theta(x) \ln(x) dx\right] =$$

$$-\int_0^{\infty} x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) \ln(x) dx = -\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\zeta\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) + 2\zeta'(z)\right]$$

Therefore

$$-\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\zeta\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) + 2\zeta'(z)\right] =$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}} \left[\zeta(1-z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) + 2\zeta'(1-z)\right]$$

is a form of the functional equation dzeta function and its derivative of 1-th order.

For z that $\zeta'(1-z) = 0$ and $\zeta(z) \neq 0$ and $\zeta(1-z) \neq 0$ and $\zeta'(z) \neq 0$

$$\text{and } \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) \neq 0 \text{ and } \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) \neq 0$$

functional equation 1-th derivative is reduced to :

$$-\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\zeta\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) + 2\zeta'(z)\right] = \Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}} \zeta(1-z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right).$$

Writing

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}} \zeta(1-z) = \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \zeta(z)$$

hence

$$-\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\zeta\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) + 2\zeta'(z)\right] = \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right)$$

$$-\zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) - 2\zeta'(z) = \zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right)$$

$$-2\zeta'(z) = \zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right) + \zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi)\right)$$

$$\zeta'(z) = -\frac{1}{2} \zeta(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) + \psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - 2\ln(\pi)\right)$$

For z that $\zeta'(z) \neq 0$ and $\zeta'(1-z) \neq 0$ and

$\zeta(z) = 0$ and $\zeta(1-z) = 0$ functional equation is reduced to :

$$-\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \zeta'(z) = \Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}} \zeta'(1-z)$$

If Riemann hypothesis is true then for $z = \frac{1}{2} + yi$

$$-\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2}} \zeta'\left(\frac{1}{2} + yi\right) = \Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2} - yi}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2} - yi}{2}} \zeta'\left(\frac{1}{2} - yi\right)$$

$$-\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2}} \zeta'\left(\frac{1}{2} + yi\right) = \overline{\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2}\right) \pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2}} \zeta'\left(\frac{1}{2} + yi\right)}$$

this equals only if $\zeta' \left(\frac{1}{2} + yi \right) = 0$ or $\Gamma \left(\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2} + yi}{2}} \zeta' \left(\frac{1}{2} + yi \right) = ci, c \in \mathbb{R}$

If Riemann hypothesis is false then

$$-\Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \zeta'(z) = \Gamma \left(\frac{1-z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}} \zeta'(1-z)$$

this equals for every z that $\zeta(z) = 0, \zeta(1-z) = 0$.

It is possible that for z that

$\zeta(z) = 0$ and $\zeta(1-z) = 0$ and

$\zeta'(z) = 0$ and $\zeta'(1-z) = 0$ functional equation 1 - th derivative is reduced to
 $0 = 0$

but in Mathematica 13 I received that

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} (\ln(x))^2 dx = (n^2)^{-z/2} \pi^{-z/2} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \left[\left(\ln(n^2 \pi) - \psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right)^2 + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right]$$

hence

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} (\ln(x))^2 dx = \\ & \frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\left(\ln(\pi n^2) - \psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right)^2 + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right] = \frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\left(\psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - \ln(\pi n^2) \right)^2 + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right] = \\ & \frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\left(\psi^2 \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - 2 \psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \ln(\pi n^2) + (\ln(\pi n^2))^2 \right) + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right] = \\ & \frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\psi^2 \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - 4 \psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \ln(n) - 2 \psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \ln(\pi) + (\ln(\pi) + 2 \ln(n))^2 + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right] = \\ & \frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[\right. \\ & \quad \left. \psi^2 \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - 4 \psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \ln(n) - 2 \psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \ln(\pi) + (\ln(\pi))^2 + 4 \ln(\pi) \ln(n) + 4 (\ln(n))^2 + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right] = \\ & \frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[4 (\ln(n))^2 - 4 \ln(n) \left(\psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \left(\psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{n=1}^\infty \int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} (\ln(x))^2 dx = \int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^2 dx = \\ & \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{1}{n^z} \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[4 (\ln(n))^2 - 4 \ln(n) \left(\psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \left(\psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \right] = \\ & \Gamma \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \\ & \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \left[4 \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{(\ln(n))^2}{n^z} - 4 \left(\psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - \ln(\pi) \right) \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{\ln(n)}{n^z} + \left(\psi \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{1}{n^z} + \psi' \left(\frac{z}{2} \right) \sum_{n=1}^\infty \frac{1}{n^z} \right] = \end{aligned}$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}}\left[4\zeta''(z)+4\zeta'(z)\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)+\zeta(z)\left\{\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)^2+\psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\right\}\right]$$

because $\theta(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}\theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2}$

hence $\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx = \int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$

$$\int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x}}\theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2}\right)(\ln(x))^2 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$-\frac{8}{(1-z)^3} - \frac{8}{z^3} + \int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-\frac{3}{2}}\theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)(\ln(x))^2 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$-\frac{8}{z^3} - \frac{8}{(1-z)^3} + \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}}\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)\theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)\left(-\ln\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)\right)^2 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$-\frac{8}{z^3} - \frac{8}{(1-z)^3} + \int_\infty^1 (t)^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}}(t)\theta(t)\left(-\ln(t)\right)^2\left(\frac{-1}{t^2}\right)dt + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$-\frac{8}{z^3} - \frac{8}{(1-z)^3} - \int_\infty^1 x^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$-\frac{8}{z^3} - \frac{8}{(1-z)^3} + \int_1^\infty x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$-\frac{8}{z^3} - \frac{8}{(1-z)^3} + \int_1^\infty \left(x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} + x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\right)\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx$$

The right – hand side is unchanged if z is replaced by $1 - z$.

Hence

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}}\left[4\zeta''(1-z)+4\zeta'(1-z)\left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)+\zeta(1-z)\left\{\left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)^2+\psi'\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)\right\}\right] =$$

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{1-z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx = \int_0^\infty x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx = -\frac{8}{(1-z)^3} - \frac{8}{z^3} +$$

$$\int_1^\infty \left(x^{\frac{1-z}{2}-1} + x^{-\frac{(1-z)}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\right)\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx = -\frac{8}{z^3} - \frac{8}{(1-z)^3} + \int_1^\infty \left(x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} + x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\right)\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1}\theta(x)(\ln(x))^2 dx =$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}}\left[4\zeta''(z)+4\zeta'(z)\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)+\zeta(z)\left\{\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)^2+\psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\right\}\right]$$

Therefore

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}}\left[4\zeta''(z)+4\zeta'(z)\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)+\zeta(z)\left(\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)^2+\psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\right)\right]=$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)$$

$$\pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}}\left[4\zeta''(1-z)+4\zeta'(1-z)\left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)+\zeta(1-z)\left(\left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)-\ln(\pi)\right)^2+\psi'\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)\right)\right]$$

is a form of the functional equation zeta function and its derivative of 2-th order.

For z that $\zeta(z) = 0$ and $\zeta(1-z) = 0$ and $\zeta'(z) = 0$ and $\zeta'(1-z) = 0$ functional equation 2 - th order is reduced to

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}}4\zeta''(z)=\Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}}4\zeta''(1-z)$$

If Riemann hypothesis is true then $z = \frac{1}{2} + yi$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}}\zeta''\left(\frac{1}{2}+yi\right)=\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2}-yi}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2}-yi}{2}}\zeta''\left(\frac{1}{2}-yi\right)$$

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}}\zeta''\left(\frac{1}{2}+yi\right)=\overline{\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}}\zeta''\left(\frac{1}{2}+yi\right)}$$

this equals only if $\zeta''\left(\frac{1}{2}+yi\right) = 0$ or $\Gamma\left(\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{\frac{1}{2}+yi}{2}}\zeta''\left(\frac{1}{2}+yi\right) = c, c \in \mathbb{R}$.

If Riemann hypothesis is false then

$$\Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}}\zeta''(z)=\Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right)\pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}}\zeta''(1-z)$$

for z that $\zeta(z)=0$ and $\zeta(1-z)=0$ and $\zeta'(z)=0$ and $\zeta'(1-z)=0$.

It is possible that for z that

$$\zeta(z) = 0 \text{ and } \zeta(1-z) = 0 \text{ and } \zeta'(z) = 0 \text{ and } \zeta'(1-z) =$$

$$0 \text{ and } \zeta''(z) = 0 \text{ and } \zeta''(1-z) = 0 \text{ functional equation 2 - th derivative is reduced to}$$

$$0 = 0$$

but in Mathematica 13 I received that

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} (\ln(x))^3 dx = -(n^2)^{-z/2} \pi^{-z/2} \Gamma$$

$$\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\left[(\ln(n^2))^3 + 3(\ln(n^2))^2 \ln(\pi) + 3 \ln(n^2)(\ln(\pi))^2 + (\ln(\pi))^3 + 3 \ln(n^2 \pi)\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\right)^2 -$$

$$\left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\right)^3 + 3 \ln(n^2 \pi)\psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - 3\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\left\{(\ln(n^2 \pi))^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)\right\} - \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right)]$$

hence

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -(\mathbf{n}^2)^{-\frac{z}{2}} \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[(\ln(\mathbf{n}^2))^3 + 3(\ln(\mathbf{n}^2))^2 \ln(\pi) + 3 \ln(\mathbf{n}^2) (\ln(\pi))^2 + (\ln(\pi))^3 + 3 \ln(\mathbf{n}^2 \pi) \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^2 - \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^3 + 3 \ln(\mathbf{n}^2 \pi) \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - 3 \psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left\{ (\ln(\mathbf{n}^2 \pi))^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right] = \\
& -\frac{1}{\mathbf{n}^z} \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[(2 \ln(\mathbf{n}))^3 + 3(2 \ln(\mathbf{n}))^2 \ln(\pi) + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) (\ln(\pi))^2 + (\ln(\pi))^3 + \right. \\
& \quad \left. 3(2 \ln(\mathbf{n}) + \ln(\pi)) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^2 - \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^3 + 3(2 \ln(\mathbf{n}) + \ln(\pi)) \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \right. \\
& \quad \left. 3 \psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left\{ (2 \ln(\mathbf{n}) + \ln(\pi))^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right] = \\
& -\frac{1}{\mathbf{n}^z} \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[8(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^3 + 12(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^2 \ln(\pi) + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) (\ln(\pi))^2 + (\ln(\pi))^3 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^2 + 3 \ln(\pi) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^2 - \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^3 + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) + 3 \ln(\pi) \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - 3 \psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left\{ 4(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^2 + 4 \ln(\mathbf{n}) \ln(\pi) + (\ln(\pi))^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right] = \\
& -\frac{1}{\mathbf{n}^z} \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[8(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^3 + 12(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^2 \ln(\pi) + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) (\ln(\pi))^2 + (\ln(\pi))^3 + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. + 3 \ln(\pi) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^2 - \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right)^3 + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) + 3 \ln(\pi) \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - 12 \psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) (\ln(\mathbf{n}))^2 \right. \\
& \quad \left. - 12 \psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \ln(\mathbf{n}) \ln(\pi) - 3 \psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) (\ln(\pi))^2 - 3 \psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right] \\
& = -\frac{1}{\mathbf{n}^z} \pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[8(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^3 - 12(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^2 \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 6 \ln(\mathbf{n}) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^3 + 3 \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} \right] = \\
& -\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[8 \frac{(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^3}{\mathbf{n}^z} - 12 \frac{(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^2}{\mathbf{n}^z} \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 6 \frac{\ln(\mathbf{n})}{\mathbf{n}^z} \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \right. \\
& \quad \left. \frac{1}{\mathbf{n}^z} \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^3 + 3 \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} \right]
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{\mathbf{n}=1}^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \mathbf{x}^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-\mathbf{n}^2 \pi \mathbf{x}} (\ln(\mathbf{x}))^3 d\mathbf{x} = -\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[\right. \\
& \quad \left. 8 \sum_{\mathbf{n}=1}^{\infty} \frac{(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^3}{\mathbf{n}^z} - 12 \sum_{\mathbf{n}=1}^{\infty} \frac{(\ln(\mathbf{n}))^2}{\mathbf{n}^z} \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 6 \sum_{\mathbf{n}=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln(\mathbf{n})}{\mathbf{n}^z} \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \right. \\
& \quad \left. \sum_{\mathbf{n}=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\mathbf{n}^z} \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^3 + 3 \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} \right] = \\
& -\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[-8 \zeta'''(z) - 12 \zeta''(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) - 6 \zeta'(z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} - \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\zeta(z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^3 + 3 \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} =$$

$$\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[8 \zeta'''(z) + 12 \zeta''(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 6 \zeta'(z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} + \right.$$

$$\left. \zeta(z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^3 + 3 \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} \right]$$

because $\theta(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2}$

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx = \int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2} \right) (\ln(x))^3 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$-\frac{48}{(1-z)^4} + \frac{48}{z^4} + \int_0^1 x^{\frac{z}{2}-\frac{3}{2}} \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) (\ln(x))^3 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\frac{48}{z^4} - \frac{48}{(1-z)^4} + \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{x}\right)^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \theta\left(\frac{1}{x}\right) \left(-\ln\left(\frac{1}{x}\right)\right)^3 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\frac{48}{z^4} - \frac{48}{(1-z)^4} + \int_\infty^1 (t)^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}} (t) \theta(t) \left(-\ln(t)\right)^3 \left(\frac{-1}{t^2}\right) dt + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\frac{48}{z^4} - \frac{48}{(1-z)^4} + \int_\infty^1 x^{-\frac{z}{2}+\frac{1}{2}} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 \left(\frac{1}{x}\right) dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\frac{48}{z^4} - \frac{48}{(1-z)^4} - \int_1^\infty x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx + \int_1^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\frac{48}{z^4} - \frac{48}{(1-z)^4} + \int_1^\infty \left(x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} - x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\right) \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx$$

The right – hand side is changed only by minus if z is replaced by $1 - z$.

Hence

$$\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{1-z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$\int_0^\infty x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx = \frac{48}{(1-z)^4} - \frac{48}{z^4} + \int_1^\infty \left(x^{\frac{1-z}{2}-1} - x^{-\frac{(1-z)}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\right) \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx =$$

$$-\left[\frac{48}{z^4} - \frac{48}{(1-z)^4} + \int_1^\infty \left(x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} - x^{-\frac{z}{2}-\frac{1}{2}}\right) \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx \right] = - \int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} \theta(x) (\ln(x))^3 dx$$

Therefore

$$-\pi^{-\frac{z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left[8 \zeta'''(z) + 12 \zeta''(z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + 6 \zeta'(z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} + \right.$$

$$\left. \zeta(z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^3 + 3 \psi'\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \psi''\left(\frac{z}{2}\right) \right\} \right] =$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \pi^{-\frac{1-z}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \left[8 \zeta''''(1-z) + 12 \zeta'''(1-z) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \right. \\ & 6 \zeta'(1-z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^2 + \psi'\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \right\} + \\ & \left. \zeta(1-z) \left\{ \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right)^3 + 3 \psi'\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \left(\psi\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) - \ln(\pi) \right) + \psi''\left(\frac{1-z}{2}\right) \right\} \right] \end{aligned}$$

is a form of the functional equation zeta function and its derivative of 3-th order.

Exists many integrals $\int_0^\infty x^{\frac{z}{2}-1} e^{-n^2 \pi x} (\ln(x))^k dx$ for $k=0,1,2,3,\dots$ so there is many functional equations of Riemann zeta function and its derivative of k-th order.

References

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